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Extended mind theory discussion paper. The next-generation mindset

Documento para discussão sobre a teoria da extended mind. A mentalidade de próxima geração

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Abstract

The paper explores political, economic, ethical/social characteristics and next-generation mindset implied from the extended mind (EM) thesis and seeks linkages to expanded memory and technological tools. The research explores the possibilities of a new mindset with a philosophical question: is the EM thesis correct, and what does it imply? There is a discussion not explored as much as comparative and transversal research about a next-generation mindset with an EM thesis. The research reveals some tendencies and relations and references authors who encompass the complex theme of expanded mind impacts. The resulting framework shows the low possibility of coordination and good outcomes generated in the next-generation mindset if the new technologies increase the technological gap, because of the EM premise.

Keywords: Extended mind, Artificial Intelligence, Next-generation Mindset.

Resumo

O artigo explora características políticas, econômicas, éticas/sociais e a mentalidade de próxima geração implícita na tese da mente estendida (EM) e busca ligações com a memória expandida e ferramentas tecnológicas. A pesquisa explora as possibilidades de uma nova mentalidade com uma questão filosófica: a tese da EM está correta e o que ela implica? Há uma discussão não explorada tanto quanto a pesquisa comparativa e transversal sobre uma mentalidade de próxima geração com uma tese da EM. A pesquisa revela algumas tendências e relações e faz referência a autores que abrangem o tema complexo dos impactos da mente expandida. A estrutura resultante mostra a baixa possibilidade de coordenação e bons resultados gerados na mentalidade de próxima geração se as novas tecnologias aumentarem a lacuna tecnológica, por causa da premissa da EM.

Palavras-chave: Mente estendida, Inteligência Artificial, Mindset de próxima geração.

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1. Introduction

Data science and computer hardware developments allow us to be more efficient, develop new knowledge, and manage complex information data sets. It is now possible to investigate almost all human knowledge and manipulate texts and objects with artificial intelligence tools. Our future mindset will be a new form of using the brain, artificial memory, and computation power.

Clark (2000) said there is no doubt there is something special about our brains. But understanding what is distinctive involves understanding both biology and technology, as well as causal and co-evolutionary influence that run between them. The question is 'How is rationality mechanically possible?'. And how explaining the production, in social, environmental, and technological context of broadly appropriate adaptive response? We should be looking at a diverse and chaotic array of explanatory resources. Exactly, we must understand how minds emerge from the complex of brain processes with bodily form, action, and the canny use of environmental structures.

The extended mind is thus, a philosophical definition that could be a basic theory and help investigate expanded memory for the next-generation mindset. According to extended mind theory (Clark and Chalmers 1998), cognitive processes are not all in the head. The brain and the characteristics of the external environment develop cognition. Cognition is a bidirectional activity that goes from the environment to the mind and vice versa. That contrasts the idea of the mind as a receptive, passive, and isolated position of what surrounds us. Using the extended mind thesis (EMT) the mind does not exclusively reside in the brain or the body but extends into the physical world. Thus, the cognitive process with that thesis is in our control when we need it. It is not permanent or exclusive of our mind, fixed in our brain cells.

It descends that the brain, in the cognition process, could be strengthened with tools. It means practical consequences and impacts are not fully investigated. When the brain uses external tools it develops an expanded memory, defined as the sum of our brain as read memory knowledge (RMK) and the extended features as read access memory (RAM). A dramatic example of that is chip implants in the brain.

Today's academy focuses on AI and competition between our brain and computer and not on the expansion and the extended mind. Thus, our paper tries to figures out the implications of the EM thesis. The human-machine interaction implications impact industrial development and were discussed in other authors' papers (Aveni 2023a, 2023b).

The paper's goal is exploring the next-generation mindset derived from a brain and its expansions and the production, in social, environmental, and technological context of broadly appropriate adaptive response. Using ChatGTP or an AI tool as a modern guru, we explore the society, political decisions and systems, and economic impacts of an EM philosophy. The bibliographic research method uses the OECD suggestion of AI use. The AI questioning technique enables us to research fields and areas and work with many references without a deep knowledge of the overall theories. The result is both an experiment and an explanation based on deep learning models provided by the ChatGTP model to see the rest of the philosophical questions about our future.

2. Methodology

The paper aim is to discuss EM theory applications and was elaborated by the author adding questions to AI ChatGTP tool (Google Open AI. ChatGTP free computer tool). The questions were: politics, economic, and social issues towards the next-generation mindset embedding the EM paradigm.

The authors provide as initial elements for the discussion: 1) Extended mind reference, 2) Brain and physical extensions references. The author is also responsible for the adaptations and complements of the resulting outcomes of AI-generated text.

According to this guide (UNESCO 2023. Figure 3: Possible ChatGPT uses in the research process pg.10), the research process with AI benefits the methodology research. As part of the mind, an AI tool could speed our comprehension of the world and develop quick responses to questions. That fits the initial thesis of the extended mind (Clark and Chalmers 1998).

Figure 1 - Methodology process

Source UNESCO (2023) figure 3 pag. 10.

Reid Hoffman wrote an Impromptu book with the ChatGPT. But AI tools must not be used to write an article but to research. There are some positive examples of it. We follow the UNESCO guideline (UNESCO 2023).

Thus, the article research for didactical use AI. If we have in mind a design or a research the AI tool helps a lot producing and review the text. An ethical attitude, however, is necessary. If we use AI tools we must declare the way was used and what part of the text was generated by it. In the present paper all the questions are reviewed by the author base on a text generated by AI. All other parts are author's self-generated. Thus, the paper is also an extended mind experiment..

3. Discussion

The question of whether a computer could have a mind has fascinated philosophers, scientists, and engineers. While the idea often appears in science fiction, the reality is more complex. First, we need the understanding of both consciousness and intelligence. With current technology, computers are merely tools or powerful, programmable machines that follow instructions without self-awareness, emotions, or understanding the famous Chinese Rooms argument (Searle 2009) about intelligence

that refuted the A. Turing's argument or the machine can learn and imitate human thought. He proposed the Turing Test as a way to test a machine's ability to think.

Philosopher John Searle's famous "Chinese Room" argument illustrates an experiment, a person inside a room follows instructions to manipulate Chinese symbols without understanding the language. To an outside observer, it might seem like the person understands Chinese. Similarly, computers today manipulate symbols (data) without understanding them and create something that has a logical structure.

About consciousness, computer processes data according to a set of instructions and don't understand it in the sense that the program is limited to causality and code. It can perform complex calculations, recognize patterns, and even simulate behaviors, but there are no motivations. But what is a Mind? The concept of a "mind" generally includes intelligence, consciousness, self-awareness, intentionality, and the capacity for thought and emotion. A mind is more than just the ability to process information; it is about experiencing that information subjectively. A mind has a mindset and defines the character of an individual and group of individuals.

A theoretic possibility of developing intelligent machines lies in the integration of machines with biological systems. Brain-computer interfaces, neural implants, and biotechnology could one day blur the line between human and machine, possibly leading to hybrid systems with mental capacities. Thus, in the future, we will have not humans and machines but humans with an extended mind and an expanded capacity.

However, there are enormous philosophical and technical hurdles to overcome. We still do not fully understand what consciousness is or how it arises. A super mind it would have also super psychological problems like humans. At last some theorists believe that consciousness may be not something that can be manufactured, and that only biological systems can be truly conscious.

Our cultural and educational systems are the results of the XX-century mindset and its technological development at that date. The new possible mind extensions are complex and must be explored and managed for the next generation. As our minds cannot manage an expanded amount of data and be as efficient 24H as machines could be, we accept an extended mind thesis to understand the complexity and the overall possible framework picture generated with that data set.

New forms of knowledge and expansion of our capacity with artificial tools need a new mindset based on historical one. The paper will explore that possible impacts in social, political, and economic fields. The discussion starts by explaining the EM thesis and the expanded brain, or mind, with today's disposable tools.

3.1 The Extended mind (EM) concept.

Andy Clark and David Chalmers proposed the extended mind thesis (EM) (1998) as an active externalism based on the active role of the environment in driving cognitive processes. That implies the environment determines some person's identity parts. The thesis complements business actions like Elon Musk's Neuralink corporation. Examples of an extended mind (EM) are IoT and all the connections with cars and virtual stored information. Following the EM we needn't store everything in the brain or storage devices, but we need to understand how to use that new opportunity.

While extended human memory management is speculative and hasn't been extensively explored, only a few authors and researchers have delved into related areas such as neuroethics, cognitive enhancement, and brain-computer interfaces.

Nick Bostrom (2019), philosopher and Director of the Future of Humanity Institute at the University of Oxford, has written extensively on topics related to artificial intelligence, transhumanism, and the future of humanity. His work often explores ethical considerations and potential risks associated with advanced technologies.

Ray Kurzweil is an author known for his writings on the singularity, the merging of humans and technology, and the potential for enhanced cognitive abilities. His book "The Singularity Is Near" (2005) discusses the exponential growth of technology and its implications for human evolution. The singularity represents a profound and disruptive transformation in human capability.

Elon Musk and Neuralink Team are working on developing brain-machine interfaces to enhance human cognition and address neurological disorders. While their focus is primarily on medical applications, the broader implications of such technologies may touch on extended human memory.

Anders Sandberg's "Ethics of Brain Emulations" (2014) paper became one of the most downloaded papers in the Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Artificial Intelligence. He is a Future of Humanity Institute researcher and has explored topics related to cognitive enhancement, ethics, and the societal implications of advanced technologies. His work often involves interdisciplinary approaches to understanding the impact of emerging technologies.

Susan Schneider (2019), philosopher and cognitive scientist, has written on topics such as the nature of consciousness, artificial intelligence, and the potential integration of technology with the human mind. Her work may provide insights into the philosophical aspects of extended cognition.

For these researchers, a way to manage a human extended memory, which involves integrating the human brain with a vast external database containing all of human knowledge, is currently speculative. However, it raises ethical, technological, philosophical, and preventive questions and risks. Here are some of them:

- Who has access to this information, and how would it be protected? That raises Ethical and Privacy Concerns.
- How is it possible to ensure the security of a human extended memory system? Safeguards would be needed to prevent unauthorized access, manipulation, or misuse of personal and collective knowledge.
- How is it possible to interface with the brain's complex neural networks? Integrating external databases with the human brain would require overcoming significant technical and biological challenges.
- How to assure Reliability and Accuracy? Misinformation or inaccuracies could have significant consequences on decision-making and understanding.
- How to secure the human-sustainable speed of data processing? The human brain has limits in terms of processing information. An excessive flow of data could potentially overwhelm individual cognitive capacities.
- By whom or what organization would have Ownership and Control or can guarantee wise scopes? Determining who owns and controls the external database integrated system would be a complex issue. It would involve legal, political, and societal considerations.
- Equality and Access? Ensuring equitable access to this extended memory system is crucial to avoid creating or exacerbating societal disparities.
- What is the sustainable Social and Cultural Impact of such a new system? It will probably impact social dynamics, education, and how knowledge is valued and transmitted across generations.

- How will be the process of Regulation and Governance? Developing regulations and governance structures to oversee the use of human extended memory would be necessary to address potential misuse and ethical concerns.
- What are the Philosophical Implications or the better result for humanity? Expanding human memory to include an external database raises philosophical questions about identity, consciousness, and what it means to be human.

The research on cognitive neuroscience, neuron ethics, and emerging technologies will provide a broader perspective on the challenges and possibilities associated with managing extended human memory dimensions.

3.2 Level of cognition and rationality, including the physical level.

Thus, an EM is a theory and not a physical extension of the brain (that could be named the expanded memory). According to Clark (2000), rationality mechanically explains the society, and technological contexts of the broadly appropriate adaptive response. Rationality is factors tuned and interanimated. The thesis hypothesis considers the mind to encompass every level of cognition and rationality, including the physical level.

We will understand that a physical extension is today a futuristic option and only experimental research exploring some disease applications of implants. According to Kandel, E. R. 2007, Medina, J. 2014, McGaugh, J. L. 2000, Dudai, Y. 2004, there are two main types of memory storage:

- Short-Term Memory (STM): Stored temporarily in the prefrontal cortex and can last for seconds to minutes. It gets transferred to long-term memory.
- Long-Term Memory (LTM): Stored in different parts of the brain, especially the hippocampus (for encoding) and the cerebral cortex (for long-term storage).

When you recall something, your brain reactivates the same neural pathways used when you first learned it. Following the academic suggestions the brain stores data through a complex network of neurons and synapses. When we learn or experience something, neurons in our brains form connections. These connections, known as synapses, strengthen when we repeatedly use or recall information. Essentially, memories are stored as patterns of these strengthened connections among neurons.

Thus, interaction between computers and the brain is possible only through Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs). These are systems that connect the brain to external devices, allowing direct communication between neurons and computers. One of the famous BCIs is Elon Musk's company Neuralink. The company is developing advanced BCIs that involve implanting tiny electrodes into the brain to read and transmit neural signals. In January 2024 Neuralink successfully implanted their first brain chip in a human patient.

Other competitors are present in the market. Synchron – Developed a stent-like BCI inserted via the bloodstream (no brain surgery required). BrainGate – Pioneers in BCIs; helped a paralyzed patient control a robotic arm with their thoughts. Kernel – Focuses on non-invasive brain-machine interfaces (wearable tech, no surgery needed). These alternatives aim to avoid invasive surgery while still enabling brain-computer interaction.

According to scholars (Lebedev and Nicolelis 2006, He and Wu, 2019, Huggins, 2020, Musk Neuralink. 2019, Binns, R. 2020, Gunkel 2020, Musk 2020, Sahakian and Morein-Zamir, 2007) Neuralink's and competitors systems consists of three main components:

- Implantable Brain Chip ("N1"). A tiny, coin-sized chip was surgically placed inside the skull.

It has ultra-thin threads (thinner than human hair) that connect to neurons in the brain.

These threads record and transmit neural activity to an external device.

- Robotic Surgical System. A high-precision robot inserts the chip's microscopic threads into the brain without damaging blood vessels. This reduces risks compared to traditional brain surgery.

- External Device & AI Software The chip communicates wirelessly with computers or smartphones. AI deciphers brain signals into meaningful actions (e.g., moving a cursor, typing).

The scholars also add that the solution carries many questions because of the unknown effects of permanent implants in the human brain: Could BCIs lead to privacy concerns or cognitive manipulation? Privacy & Security Risks. Brain implants collect neural data, which could be hacked or misused. Who owns this brain data—the user, Neuralink, or a third party?

Could governments or corporations exploit BCIs for surveillance or control? How will the brain react after years of having a foreign object inside? If AI can read/write brain signals, can thoughts be influenced or manipulated? What if a company, government, or hacker alters someone's thoughts, emotions, or memories?

A threat is that brain-computer interfaces could create a "tech elite" or wealthy individuals may enhance intelligence, leaving others behind. This could lead to "neural class divisions" where some have superhuman abilities while others don't. These concerns must be discussed before the end of experimentation oriented to reduce diseases successfully. However experimental implants could be purchased without legislation today and the trust in legislation is fake because, as we all know, system tricks are always possible and involve both people and criminal associations.

Innovations are not easy to control and computer-brain manipulation could be developed with other techniques and nano-biological solutions in the future thus, the problem is the BCI definition and innovation and research. No control and legislation could stop research and innovation. A defensive attitude and a series of battles were fought by the Catholic Church against innovation a progress resulting in defeats. It is a utopia to expect a different result.

To be pragmatic we must expect innovations and new paradigms. The only way to handle it is to be prepared and have ethics and education to understand potential risks. It is possible to establish alternative risk-avoiding and reduction strategies and educate people to handle them. However, the physical extension of the brain with some computer devices is today only sci-fiction narrative. Today the extended mind could be handled with a framework of information inclusion management practices. In other words, we must start to imagine a different approach to information and information systems to include information technology not only for communication.

A different approach means imagining tools of technology disposable free for all and the level of innovations increases when not only some academic research will be developed but many hundred thousand, or million, practices will develop their research. What will happen if some group of nerds in the place to develop hacker

techniques (that seems more interesting because, in the short term, they could steal some dollars from the systems) become addicted to genome research and experiment with viruses or genetic clones? And if some criminal organization uses hidden profits to finance such research? And if terroristic organizations will develop not an air crash but an uncontrolled virus attack?

We bet that no government is prepared to handle risks, as they do with COVID-19 and a potential conflict expanded as a world war. There is no overall protection with actual democratic or other government. The potential threats that could be developed by singles or small groups are impossible to stop or control, even with actual information systems. Examples of that are serious threats to information systems. Every day we experiment with such attacks on our phones and computers. Another example is the so-called “lone wolf” terrorist attacks that are performed even in the most accredited National security systems. Last but not least the madness of phyco's attacks in schools or shopping centers.

The rationality central question of an extended mind could be seen from a provocative point of view. According to Harari's (2017) book *Homo Deus* organisms are just algorithms and life is just data processing. However, the question is: is intelligence more valuable than consciousness (our subjective experience of sensations, emotions, and thoughts)? Can non-conscious but intelligent algorithms know us better than we know ourselves? The underlying algorithms that describe, pattern, and predict human behavior are utopia and are not what matters. As Harari would have known, because of his historical education, the history of humankind was impossible to predict.

Harari's evangelist attitude or the arrogance to explain to others what is right and what isn't is a psychological problem caused by ego. So *Homo Deus* is an explication of what the *Homo Deus* Harari think is the reality but is not. Some other are accredited academics are trying to explain the human-technology relationship and new sociologist impacts like Bauman, Giddens, and Sartre.

3.3 Biases and problems of cognitive process

According to some authors (Kahneman 2002, Ariely 2008, Kahneman 2012, Gardner and Tetlock 2015, Kahneman, Sibony and Sunstein, 2021), while the Extended Mind allows humans to offload cognitive tasks onto external systems, cognitive biases can distort decision-making by influencing how we interact with these external extensions. Recognizing these biases is crucial to optimizing our extended cognition, especially in technology-driven environments like trading, finance, and decision-making (Kahneman 2002).

Cognitive biases can significantly influence the Extended Mind Theory: when using search engines or AI assistants, people tend to seek information that confirms their existing beliefs, reinforcing cognitive echo chambers; people often rely too heavily on the first piece of information they receive (the "anchor"), even when using extended tools like spreadsheets, calculators, or AI assistants; people trust automated systems and external devices more than their own reasoning, even when those systems are flawed; the ease of recalling certain events affects judgments, especially when using external sources like social media or financial news; when cognition is extended into social groups, biases like groupthink (the tendency to conform to a group's consensus) can override individual critical thinking; and people overvalue digital assets they own (NFTs, cryptocurrencies) just because they possess them, even when external data suggests otherwise.

Examples of how cognitive biases influence the Extended Mind across different fields:

1 - A doctor using AI diagnostic software might over-rely on its recommendations and overlook symptoms that the AI fails to detect. This can lead to misdiagnoses because the doctor defers critical thinking to the AI.

2. Decision-makers often rely too much on the first piece of information they receive, even if it's outdated. A CEO who initially values a startup at \$1 billion may struggle to adjust their expectations, even after new market trends suggest it's worth less. The result is overpaying for acquisitions or ignoring competitive risks.

3. Traders use external tools (news, AI models, forums) but only seek information that supports their existing beliefs. A crypto investor bullish on Bitcoin may only follow analysts predicting price increases, ignoring warnings of potential crashes. The result is a poor risk management and financial losses.

4. People judge the likelihood of events based on how easily they recall similar cases, often using external knowledge sources like Google or Wikipedia. A student preparing for an exam might focus more on topics that frequently appear in search results rather than those that are actually important for the test. The consequence is skewed learning priorities and inefficient studying.

5. When thinking is extended into social groups (online forums, communities), people conform rather than critically analyze information. A social media movement might spread misinformation because people assume "if everyone believes it, it must be true." We will have viral misinformation can influence elections, public policy, and personal beliefs. Solution:

Not all practical techniques to counteract cognitive biases in Extended Mind environments. It is difficult use Human-AI Hybrid Decision-Making, always compare new data to different sources when all information rely on computers, propose opposite Argument and Diversified Data Sources, Data-Driven Thinking. Even the Devil's Advocate Rule or designate someone to challenge group assumptions in meetings or discussions.

Ask yourself, "If I didn't own this, would I buy it today at this price?" Or to have third-Person Evaluation using rational exit strategies like a crypto investor sets a stop-loss order to prevent emotional decision-making during price crashes, could be the only solution.

4 . AI Discussion: questions and answers

4.1 What are the Socio Political considerations about next generation mindset?

An extended mind concept produces a new mindset. The elite theory by Mosca, Pareto, Michels, and Gramsci (Volpe 2021) states that the political system is dominated by groups or lobbies, not by the media vote. After the election, a party and the majority vote dominate the parliament. But extended minds don't exist as a lobby in parliament. An extended mindset will fit elites capacity to develop new dominance.

That new mind will be necessary to develop a new democratic political and economic system. We need a flexible and focused system at the same time. For example, assume some operational activities of all government and public administration must concentrate on objectives, and these must have goal-oriented leaders. We must also assume flexible teams and strategies must orient these operational activities to benefit new forms of work and public services productions like education and digital services.

The books of authors like Harari (2014, 2017, 2018, 2020, 2022) are sold and widely accepted by low or medium-educated people. Most academics focus on transformations of particular economic activities, ethics, or political correctness, and, on the other side, some entrepreneurs or practitioners discuss some aspects of the business or even new technologies.

But human future and next-generation mindset appear fragmented between specialists. Following the debate by Susan Schneider (Schneider 2019), the situation faces a massive bad communication of useless communications. Which new political mindset will benefit all? A new democratic political system must be flexible and encompass an extended mind, and, at the same time, it must be multicultural. The future of human beings, somehow, was removed by the actual debate concentrated on more reduced and tactical questions.

In this paper, we advocate the need for a new political strategy and a new ideology about our human beings, and facing this power resulting from the joint technical and information process. In other papers, we discuss the terms Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0 (Aveni 2023a, 2023b) as an economic new paradigm not only because it could cause conflict in definitions but also because the definition is confused.

Our paper about ethics and economy (Aveni 2022) discusses the idea that ethics and political economy and Complexity planning could orient and give some tools to include those discussions in an overall comprehension of reality. The idea of a next-generation political mindset changing the political system faces world complexity. The different cultures will develop mindsets that could impact and have different approaches to politics and democracy.

The question of whether it is possible to have democracy in a world divided by religions and different cultural approaches is complex and depends on various factors here summarized in the following table.

The success of a democratic system in societies requires ongoing efforts, adaptability, and a commitment to the principles of democratic governance. History and the first political philosophers like Montesquieu and Rousseau, had told diverse societies cannot develop and sustain democratic systems that respect individual rights and foster inclusive political participation in a thousand years, so it is difficult to expect a new system to develop in short. The specific approach and success vary based on the unique cultural and historical society.

Table 1 - Political Mindset

Political mindset Threats	
Political Representation.	Ensuring diverse representation in political institutions is crucial for a democratic society. This representation can help address the concerns and interests of different communities.
Civil Society and Social Institutions.	The strength of civil society and social institutions can play a crucial role in supporting democracy in culturally diverse environments. When diverse groups are free to organize, express their views, and participate in civic life, it contributes to a vibrant democratic society.

Political mindset Threats	
Rule of Law and Human Rights.	A robust democracy often relies on the rule of law and the protection of human rights. Establishing a legal framework that upholds individual freedoms and prevents discrimination based on religion or culture is essential for a functioning democracy.
Secularism.	Many successful world democracies operate on the principle that the state remains neutral in matters of religion. That helps ensure equal treatment of individuals regardless of their religious or cultural affiliations.
Education and Awareness.	Promoting education and awareness about democratic values, tolerance, and pluralism can help bridge cultural and religious divides. An informed and engaged citizenry is essential for the success of democratic systems.
Cultural Pluralism and Democracy.	Democracy, in its essence, is a political system that allows for the representation and participation of diverse voices and perspectives. Cultural and religious diversity can be democracy compatible as long as there is a commitment to inclusivity and respect for individual rights.
Dialogue and Reconciliation.	Open and respectful dialogue between groups can foster, understand, and contribute to social cohesion. Efforts toward reconciliation and conflict resolution are vital in diverse societies.
Extremism.	Extremist ideologies, whether rooted in religion or culture, can pose challenges to democracy. Efforts to counter extremism and promote moderation are urgent for maintaining a stable democratic environment.

Source: Author elaboration with author's ChatGTP.

Technological progress will not benefit the world population if not controlled by ethics. We fear a Big Brother (ORWELL 1949) problem in the future concentrating on a monopoly of information, data management, and information possession. That is the opposite idea i.e. of Reid Hoffman (2022) and others. We fear in the future, after resources (petrol) and natural resources (like water and land) war due to information and knowledge monopolies. World population limits city concentration, and the increase in poverty will increase these risks. But political management of world society could drive a decrease in liberty if EM will benefit only a few people.

As a political variable, the reduction of liberty depends on the gap between new information and knowledge and the political management of that new power. That is an open relation and a question for the future. A new mindset is transversal and impacts all human activities. The free access to information allows people to avoid fakes and see the reality of things if they are trained.

It is well known that China employs a comprehensive internet censorship system, and content control refers to the Great Firewall of China (GFW). (Griffiths 2021, Roberts 2018, Deibert 2012, 2013, MacKinnon 2012, Murong Xuecun (慕容雪

村) 2010). The primary aim of this system is to regulate and restrict access to certain foreign websites and online content that the Chinese government considers sensitive or a potential threat to its political stability.

The level and methods of internet censorship vary widely from country to country, and not all censorship systems are as extensive or sophisticated as in China. Some nations restrict access to certain websites or content for national security, political stability, or cultural considerations. Examples of countries with notable internet censorship systems:

-Iran: Iran has implemented strict internet censorship, known as the National Internet, which restricts access to some websites, including social media platforms and news outlets.

-North Korea: North Korea has one of the most isolated and heavily censored internet environments globally, with limited access to the global internet. The government tightly controls online content and access.

-Russia: Russia has implemented various measures to control internet content, including blocking access to websites and social media platforms. The country has also introduced legislation requiring data storage within the country.

-Turkey: Turkey blocked access to social media platforms and news websites during some periods of political unrest. The government employs both legal and technical measures for internet censorship.

-Saudi Arabia: Saudi Arabia has strict internet censorship policies that target content deemed contrary to Islamic values, as well as political and social issues

Several countries with majority Muslim populations have implemented various forms of internet censorship and content control. However, the approaches to censorship vary widely among Islamic countries, and the reasons for censorship may range from political and social concerns to cultural and religious considerations.

The actual political struggle is a slippery field and full of fake and information manipulations. Fake news is false or misleading information (misinformation, including disinformation, propaganda, and hoaxes) that has the aim of damaging the reputation of a person or entity. Although false news has always been spread throughout history, today, the expansion of communication and media extends the novel and percentage of fake news. Disinformation involves spreading false information using articles, misinterpreted genuine facts, and articles that employ sensationalist or clickbait headlines not supported in the text.

A firewall against the prevalence of fake news from political polarization, post-truth politics, motivated reasoning, confirmation bias, and social media algorithms is good when the ethics and self-regulation of public and private media are out of control or oriented only by influencers and not by personal criticism. Of course, we differentiate it from censure, but it is clear that democratic governments that own or could manipulate social media and news, more populist regimes like in South America, are applying different forms of censure and faking news to orient public opinion.

Will the next generation find a solution or a new political mindset puzzle being the dominant or political elite? However, the situation seems oriented to a struggle between political powers to dominate and fake news in almost all countries. In other words, generally, communication lacks objectivity and nobody wants to change it because strong powers use it. Will the next-generation political mindset, with an expanded free memory, have the power to change it for the better?

4.2 What are the Economy consideration about next-generation mindset?

The next-generation mindset will impact the economy but primarily with the exchange factors rate and the currency to be used. What will be the transaction currency the next-generation mindset deals with? How people will be paid for the labor? Which will be the general transaction medium of exchange? It will be unrealistic to change the dollar with a new currency or bitcoin?

Actually most of global exchanges are in some way referred to dollars or a standard money issued in the U.S. Dollar, as all money has the function of reserve of value, unit of account, and medium of exchange. The changing proposal of the global reserve currency from the U.S. dollar to a new global accepted currency is complex and challenging. Several factors contribute to the difficulty of such a transition in literature and economic discussions. New digital money as Bitcoin has a well-known history that is like a share of a private company without the characteristics of a currency, primarily because there is no national bank or a network of banks that guarantees its value.

The stability and economic strength of the issuing country play the acceptance of a currency as a global reserve. Challenges in Countries' economic and political stability proposing a new currency could hinder its adoption. (Eichengreen 2010, Obstfeld and Taylor 2004, Gourinchas and Rey 2007). While discussions about an alternative global reserve currency have taken place, the practical challenges and the vested interests associated with the U.S. dollar have made a rapid and complete shift to a new currency unrealistic in the near term. Thus it is unrealistic to change dollar supremacy with a new currency based on the factors that historically have made it challenging to replace the U.S. dollar as the global reserve currency.

The dollar currency will continue in the future, and the expansion of BRICS (Kolesnichenko, Rozanov and Debin 2016) and the world economy will continue without change the dollar supremacy. The growth of world countries without the USA is increasing, and it will be impossible to have a single country predominance as it was late in the last century. However, the growth of the next future is concentrated in a few countries. This unbalanced economy and asymmetrical economic power will need more and more intervention for risk-free and low turbulence, and the only solution is a coordinated and mutual intervention of a team of countries.

Thus, the actual economy growth percentage will be based primarily on the third sector growth the information economy, and its activities as the spearhead of growth. This sentence will hide the reality of the world economic growth as an absolute value. That is because the "marginalist" neoclassical economic mainstream focuses on increasing variations of GNP. The global economy needs an increase in volumes even if they are at a low increase margin. Another problem with "marginal" narrow vision is the lack of patrimonial accuracy. In other words, some countries are richer not because of the growth they have at present but because of capital. They have sovereignty over land and people. In other words, as the same World Bank admits, the GDP is not enough to measure the wealth of a nation. In particular, according to World Bank (2021), we must measure procured capital, natural capital, human capital, and net foreign assets. Some reports present a different country's classification of the usual.

One issue is the wealth perceived and another is the happiness of people living in the country. It is a simple fact, always forgotten by economists, that preference varies and is not an objective variable observed and used to build a preference curve and a demand curve because the configuration varies from time to time and locally. It is a probabilistic curve. That means a substantial difference between the marketing predictions and cost of marketing predictions and the reality observed, the cause-effect

relationship claimed by statistical analysis. Or, to say the same, statistics are worthwhile only if the hypotheses are confirmed. The probability awareness is known.

In such a world of uncertainty, we use statistical tools and models to decide not only the best choice or even the better strategy but also to orient our choices and reduce risks. But in reality, if we consider a certain amount of variables in economic models if we raise several such variables, the probabilistic result over a couple of thousand measures is nearly the same as the average of the first couple of thousand, or we extract models from information research.

Following the logic above, new models and observations choosing the better strategy will be necessary for every risk. That a process never developed because it is recursive and needs a lot of calculation capacity. We believe good statistics support our decisions. In reality, we decide at risk of failure because we decide with poor information, and we make decisions almost by intuition.

Intuition is the non-sequential information-processing mode. It differs from the deliberative style of decision-making. Intuition is a subjective decision for most of us. It can influence judgment through either emotion or cognition, and specific ways intuition influences decisions remain poorly understood (Kahneman 2002, Klein and Bolders 2016, Smith 1999, Gigerenzer 2004, Thaler 1992)

The next generation's economic mindset will face enormous challenges to change the economy based on capitalism and currencies. The mainstream economic models cannot orient choices with an extended mindset that could calculate better some economic variables than old research public structures and models.

But when we look for economic laws we need to understand some differences between the economic laws explained under Christianity and another cultural background. Islamic economics, as guided by Sharia (Islamic law), is a system that aims to promote economic and social justice while adhering to the principles outlined in the Quran and the teachings of Prophet Muhammad. The Chinese approach is based on Confucianism and Marxist theory adapted to China by Mao Tse-tung.

Following Weber's comparative sociology, Buss (2015) approached the Economic Ethics of World Religions and their Laws. The Occident has developed a capitalistic system that never existed elsewhere. That is connected to the democracy and its system. In our analysis of the book Western capitalism, was supported by rational science and technology. The differences between the Christian, Sharia (Islamic), and Confucian points of view on the economy follow the next table.

Thus, it is clear that some common dimensions of the different cultures affect the practical international relationship that is rivalry-based. Human rights declaration and sustainable development and a world organization for peace like ONU are supported by all countries and cultures only as general intentions. The operational and practice relationship almost always shows the conflict between saying and doing reflecting different cultures.

Table 2 - Religion diversity

Religion social vision diversity	
Christianity:	Emphasis on Charity: Christianity encourages charity, and the concept of "love thy neighbor" is central. This is reflected in the promotion of social welfare and assistance to those in need.
	Ethical Business Practices: Christian teachings emphasize honesty, integrity, and ethical conduct in economic activities. Exploitation and unjust practices are discouraged.
	Private Property Rights: Christianity generally supports the right to private property, but with the understanding that wealth should be used responsibly for the greater good.
Sharia (Islamic Law):	Prohibition of Riba (Usury/Interest): Sharia strictly prohibits the charging or paying of interest. Islamic finance promotes profit-and-loss sharing arrangements.
	Wealth Distribution: Sharia emphasizes equitable wealth distribution through mandatory charity (Zakat). Social justice and economic balance are crucial principles.
	Ethical Investments: Sharia-compliant investments avoid activities that are considered haram (forbidden), such as gambling or the production of alcohol.
Confucianism:	Social Harmony: Confucianism emphasizes social harmony and stability, reflected in economic policies that seek to maintain order and avoid disruptive changes.
	Ethical Conduct in Business: Confucian values stress ethical behavior in business transactions, with an emphasis on honesty, integrity, and social responsibility.
	Meritocracy and Education: Confucianism values education and a meritocratic system, suggesting economic policies that support education and reward individuals based on their abilities.
	Long-Term Perspective: Confucianism promotes a long-term perspective and sustainable development, potentially influencing economic policies that favor gradual progress over rapid changes.

Source: Author elaboration with author's ChatGTP.

Economic governance could not be global, currency and exchange rates will have to accept diversities. The fragmentation of economies and their cultural background are aggregated into blocks to defend countries by aggregating into a stronger international block is an important practice in the last decades and follows cultural background more than economic interests.

Will a next-generation mindset be able to perform new models and forms of trade and competition including social economy (or third sector) and multicultural capitalism? The pessimistic answer is that it is not possible to transform organizations like WTO to help development. Thus, how will be the dynamic of economy and labor and the exchange rate of production factors with a next generation mindset?

4.3 What are Ethic and Society impacts of next-generation mindset?

The last dimension of the research is social. Some prominent trends and shifts in the future are in the following table.

Table 3 - Social Trends in XXI century

Change Trends in he XXI Century	
Demographic Changes	Shifts in population dynamics, including aging populations in some regions and youth bulges in others, have had significant social and economic implications. Africa will increase the number of people more than Asia and other countries in the future decades.
Migration and Displacement	increased migration and displacement due to conflict, environmental issues, and economic disparities.
Political Global Changes	The 21st century has seen political shifts, including the rise of populist movements, changes in global power dynamics, and increased political polarization.
Technological Advancements	The rapid development and widespread adoption of digital technologies, particularly the internet and smartphones, have transformed communication, access to information, and various industries.
Rise of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Advances in AI and automation have impacted various industries, raising questions about job displacement and ethical considerations.
Globalization	Increase interconnectedness and interdependence among countries, economies, and cultures, leading to a more globalized world.
Education Transformation	changes in education delivery methods, including online learning, and a greater emphasis on lifelong learning and skill development.
Social Media	The rise of social media platforms has significantly impacted communication, activism, and information dissemination.
Climate Change Awareness	Growing awareness of environmental issues, particularly climate change, has increased global efforts to address sustainability and reduce carbon emissions.

Change Trends in the XXI Century	
Changing Work Patterns	The rise of remote work, gig economy jobs, and a focus on work-life balance have altered traditional employment structures.
Health Pandemics Risks	The 21st century has witnessed significant global health challenges, including the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasizing the need for global cooperation in public health.
Advancements in Medicine and Healthcare	Breakthroughs in medical research, genomics, and healthcare technology have improved treatment options, extended life expectancy, and enhanced overall healthcare.
Energy Transition	growing emphasis on renewable energy sources and transition away from fossil fuels in response to climate change concerns.

Source: Author elaboration with author's ChatGTP.

These trends are interconnected, and their impacts vary across regions and communities. Several authors and scholars have written extensively about the social changes in the 21st century (Joseph E. Stiglitz 2002, Manuel Castells 2000, Samuel P. Huntington 1996) Predicting the characteristics of the next society in the 21st century involves a degree of uncertainty and speculation. People must consider ongoing trends and emerging developments numbered before.

The actual morale and ethics mainstream work with the concept of political correctness. Correctness, especially in the context of political correctness, has been explored by various thinkers and philosophers like J.S. Mill for his advocacy of individual liberties and the importance of free speech, Herbert Marcuse explores how tolerance can suppress dissent, and it has implications for discussions on the correctness and regulation of language, Michel Foucault on how language can be a tool of power and control, Judith Butler in feminist and queer theory, Richard Rorty with the idea that language is a tool for achieving social harmony and justice.

Unfortunately, these ideas became radical, and the morale turned to political correctness's today's configuration and killed all social criticism out of influencers' will. Thus, the Big Brother paradox became not a direct control by dictatorships but a more subtle coercion, an indirect formalism based on communication channel ownership.

The influencers and some social media use the actual political correctness mainstream to orient communication. They create a virtual barrier between political and social groups against others. It's the opposite of the political correctness of early philosophers' ideas or a means against dictatorship and national political barriers. People without criticism and filtering tools are subjected to these influences.

The idea that political correctness may distort moral discourse or principles is a perspective held by some authors. It's important to note that views on this matter vary widely, and different people may have different assessments of the impact of political correctness on morality.

A few arguments that critics make regarding how political correctness potentially distorts moral discussions: 1) suppression of Free Speech may lead to self-censorship and a reluctance to engage in open and honest discussions about moral issues; 2) moral Relativism implies overemphasis on political correctness can lead to moral

relativism, where all moral viewpoints are considered equally valid; 3) inhibition of moral criticism may discourage people from critiquing certain practices or beliefs, even when there may be legitimate moral concerns; 4) devaluation of Individual Responsibility may, in some cases, shift the focus from individual responsibility to group identity.

The debate over political correctness and its impact on morality is complex, and different individuals and communities may have varying perspectives on whether it enhances or distorts moral discussions. In recent years the European Union also became politically correct like the USA under the progressive leadership of left political parties in Europe. Some critics of that came from Douglas Murray (2017,2020). Some issues are in work opportunities, entrepreneurship, startups, and new businesses that change society and wealth. The new society will need new education or new professional skills in the future. What is the final goal of a politically correct society?

These areas of criticism are likely also areas for new activities and innovation of a next-generation mindset. The pessimistic result came from analyzing social and ethical changes. Would the next-generation mindset be able to encompass all these changes and build a new society? Which ethics apply to guarantee wealth for all? Is it possible to trust that in a few decades against centuries? Will it be possible to educate a generation to respect nature, humans, and the biological environment without correctness but with respect? Will Pareto law limit or paradox suppurate and changes will be useful and not compromise the next generations like today? These are some questions not easy to respond to.

5. Discussion results

AI tool uses deep learning methods to elaborate philosophical answers elaboration to questioning. The result is research on the internet or in the digital repository the tool explored. It could be a normal answer by middlemen. We must also consider the questions to discuss the global point of view and not only the Western philosophy. It is difficult to verify but the AI program do not assess (and it also because there are internet block forbidding it) for instance Asiatic, African and other cultures.

Because of political, economic, and social changes due to increasing technological advances and a next-generation mindset with the extended memory, it is difficult to predict how and what outcome in the future on the different areas. It belongs to human sciences to develop models to design the new political, economic, and future social framework. We must avoid quantitative-based models without political and social variables. The new wealth and welfare qualitative goals need qualitative models based also on moral and philosophical methods (AVENI 2021).

However, the EM thesis and expanded mind tools did not find on the internet a next-generation mindset embedding a global ethic that benefits the economy and society with politically wise governance, and the use of expanded memories. As in the last decades, Political and Social Systems will decide our future by the political elites and economic power of a few corporations and leaders with few moral considerations. We argue that corporations, or governments, are the organizations that mainly will manipulate information and define future human-machine activities or an extended mindset.

Thus, expanded tools, or the Internet of Things (IoT), will help to have under control devices and extensions of goods like houses, cars, or services like access to housekeeping and travel. In the future, the ones who will have access to codes and information, or only some people of the next generation, will be advantaged and have access to a whole set of benefits more than people or poor people.

Without a change in education, an old mindset will continue to dominate. It is difficult to change cultural beliefs. However, we must develop new systems or models to help the brain work and process information without old models and fakes. Presumably, the next generation's mindset will be attracted by strong powers and corporations not because of the salary but because the information manipulation will guarantee access to the goods and services of the last generation. The result of our research is the extended mind will increase the wealth of only a few people's skills and cognitive abilities.

It will always be possible to meet a place where the latest innovations will be disposable for elites, even with cultural differences. The extended mind will be a new status for elites like the aristocracy in the Middle Ages, not a benefit for all. At last, the analysis shows that political, economic, and social systems will leave only a narrow window to benefit everyone with new technologies like extended minds because the systems need a dramatic and quick change. Still, there is opposition to doing it by the actual political, economic, and social dominant systems.

Table 4 - Obstacles to new mindset

Politics	No recent changes in political systems and democracy world-wide. Augmented authoritarian tendencies.
	Firewalls to free information and democracy. Fakes and communications manipulation increase.
	Cultural and religion obstacles
Economic	Struggle for currency and transactions between nations
	What is wealth questioning
	Economic decision making models
	Cultural and religion influence on economy
Social	Understand and face multiple trends and impacts
	Struggle to correctness and morale
	New Ethic and welfare

Source: Author: Alessandro Aveni. alessandro@unb.br. 2024

4. Concluding remarks

With the limitation of the AI used to answer some questions, and the western culture as main source of discussion, the paper explained the frontier of the next-generation mindset starting from the EM thesis. The framework outcome is difficult to understand and manage. Academy has little experience and complexity models to use and less planning experience of complexity that include, at the same time, political, economic, and social changes. A wide discussion must be integrated with other cultures point of view (for example, Indian, Islamic and Chinese).

The EM thesis clarifies only we have more tools and devices to help us find a way to change our future for the better. An expanded memory and other technological features are tools we can use more and more. However, ethical, social, and economic contexts cannot be transformed with technological tools alone. Innovation and AI could increase the gap between people using an old mindset, a no-western, and a new technological-aided mindset. In other words increase the fragmentation and differences between people.

The research final framework shows instability and weak social equilibrium that could lead to a future with more conflicts than today's. We need new education and cognitive ideas and practices we aren't developing today. A better future is not only an economic, political, or ethical model but a chaotic mixture of probabilistic and intuition-driven flexible decisions. EM mindset will help us to manage complexity especially if we all use expanded memory and technological tools, but we must understand how to use it wisely.

Referências

Ariely, Dan. **Predictably Irrational**, Harper Collins. 2008, ISBN 978-0-06-135323-9

Aveni A. Industry 5.0 and industry 4.0 comparative definitions. **Revista Processus de Estudos de Gestão, jurídicos e Financeiros** v. 14 n. 46. 2023a.
<https://periodicos.processus.com.br/index.php/egjf/article/view/933>

Aveni A. Industry 5.0 narrative: utopia and reality. **Revista JRG de Estudos Acadêmicos**, Ano 6, Vol. VI, n.13, jul.-dez., 2023b . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8055689
ARK: 57118/JRG.v6i13.624

AVENI, A.. Complexity planning comparative approaches. **Revista JRG de Estudos Acadêmicos**. v.5, p.537 - 551, 2022.
Home page: [<https://http://revistajrg.com/index.php/jrg>][doi:10.5281/zenodo.7411673]

Aveni, A. A responsabilidade e ética são um bom negócio e entram no capital imaterial da empresa. **Revista Coleta Científica**. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6484963. , v.V, p.69 - 82, 2021. <http://portalcoleta.com.br/index.php/rcc>. 2021.

Binns, R.. Neuralink: The Ethics of Brain-Computer Interfaces. **Journal of Medical Ethics**, 46(8), 506-508. 2020.

Bostrom, Nick (September 2019). "The Vulnerable World Hypothesis" (<https://doi.org/10.1111%2F1758-5899.12718>). **Global Policy**. 10 (4): 455–476. 2019. doi:10.1111/1758-5899.12718 (<https://doi.org/10.1111%2F1758-5899.12718>).
Kurzweil, Ray (2005). *The Singularity is Near*. New York: Viking Books. ISBN 978-0-670-03384-3.

Buss, Andreas. **The Economic Ethics of World Religions and their Laws An Introduction to Max Weber's Comparative Sociology**. 2015 ISBN 978-3-8487-2424-6 (Print) 978-3-8452-6583-4 (ePDF). From https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/id/f719de75-8b55-4c2a-8781-69a2ddc7fe1f/external_content.pdf

Castells M. **The rise of the network society**. Blackwell Publishers, Oxford, 2000

Clark A. Reasons, Robots and the Extended Mind (Rationality for the New Millennium). **Mind and Language** 16:2: 2001 p.121-145. 2000

Clark A. e Chalmers David J., The Extended Mind, **Analysis**, vol. 58, n. 1, January 1998, pp. 7-9, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3328150>.

Deibert, Ronald J, and Masashi Crete-Nishihata. Global governance and the spread of cyberspace controls. **Global Governance: A Review of Multilateralism and International Organizations** 18 (3):339-61.2012.

Deibert, Ronald J. **Black Code: Inside the Battle for Cyberspace**. Signal. 2013 ISBN 10: 0771025335 / ISBN 13: 9780771025334

Dudai, Y.. The Neurobiology of Consolidations, Or, How Stable is the Engram?. **Annual Review of Psychology**, 55, 51-86. 2004.

Eichengreen B., Exorbitant Privilege. The Rise and Fall of the Dollar and the Future of the International Monetary System, **Oxford: Oxford University Press**, 2010, 224 pages, ISBN: 780-199753789

Gigerenzer G. Mindless statistics. **The Journal of Socio-Economics** 33 587–606. Max Planck Institute for Human Development, Lentzeallee 94, 14195 Berlin, Germany.2004.

Gourinchas, Pierre-Olivier, and Helene Rey. International Financial Adjustment. **Journal of Political Economy**, vol. 115, no. 4, 2007, pp. 665–703. JSTOR, <https://doi.org/10.1086/521966>. Accessed 19 Jan. 2024.

Griffiths, James **The Great Firewall of China** - London : Bloomsbury Publishing, 2021 - 440 p. - ISBN: 9781350257931 - Permalink: <http://digital.casalini.it/9781350257931> - Casalini id: 5214414

Gunkel, D. J. The Machine Question: Critical Perspectives on AI, Robots, and Ethics. **MIT Press**. 2020.

Harari Y.N. **Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind** London: Harvill Secker, 2014. ISBN 978-006-231-609-7

_____**Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow**, ISBN 978-1-910701-88-1. 2016. Money: Vintage Minis (select excerpts from Sapiens and Homo Deus. London: Penguin Random House, ISBN 978-1-78487-402-5.

_____**21 Lessons for the 21st Century**. London: Jonathan Cape, 2018), ISBN 1-78733-067-2

He, H., and Wu, D. **Brain-Computer Interfaces: Principles and Applications**. 2019. Springer.

Hebb, D. O. . **The Organization of Behavior: A Neuropsychological Theory**. 1949. Wiley. (Introduced the concept of "Hebbian Learning" (neurons that fire together, wire together).

Huggins, J. (2020). **Neuralink and the Brain's Future**. MIT Press.

Huntington, Samuel P. **The clash of civilizations and the remaking of world order**. SIMON & SCHUSTER. 1996.

International Bank for Reconstruction and Development. The World Bank **The changing wealth of the nations 2021**. Managing Assets for the Future

Kahneman D.. Maps of bounded rationality: a perspective on intuitive judgment and choice. Prize Lecture, December 8, 2002 **Princeton University, Department of Psychology, Princeton, NJ 08544, USA**

Kahneman D. **Thinking, Fast and Slow**. Macmillan. Retrieved April 8, 2012. ISBN 978-1-4299-6935-2

Kahneman, Daniel; Sibony, Olivier; Sunstein, Cass (16 May 2021). **Noise: A Flaw in Human Judgment**. New York: Little, Brown Spark. pp. 37–38. 2021. ISBN 978-0-00-830899-5. OCLC 1242782025. Retrieved 28 February 2022

Kandel, E. R. In Search of Memory: The Emergence of a New Science of Mind. 2007. W. W. Norton & Company.

Klein, G., and Borders, J. The ShadowBox approach to cognitive skills training: An empirical evaluation. **Journal of Cognitive Engineering and Decision Making**, 10(3), 268-280. 2016.

Kolesnichenko O., Rozanov, A. and Debin L. The Role of BRICS in Global Politics. **Globalistics and Globalization Studies** 2016 277–282. 2016. From https://www.sociostudies.org/upload/sociostudies.org/almanac/globalistics_and_globalization_studies_5/277-282.pdf

Lebedev, M. A., & Nicolelis, M. A. L.. "Brain–machine interfaces: past, present and future." **Trends in Neurosciences**, 29(9), 536-546.2006
McGaugh, J. L.. Memory—A Century of Consolidation. **Science**, 287(5451), 248-251.2000.

MacKinnon, Rebecca. **Consent of the Networked : the World-Wide Struggle for Internet Freedom**. New York :Basic Books, 2012.

Medina, J.. **Brain Rules: 12 Principles for Surviving and Thriving at Work, Home, and School**. 2014. Pear Press.

Murong Xuecun. **Leave Me Alone: A Novel of Chengdu**. Translated by Harvey Thomlinson. Allen&Unwin. Autralia. 2010.

Murray, D. **The Madness of Crowds: Gender, Race and Identity**. Bloomsbury Continuum. 2020.

Murray, D. **Strange Death of Europe: Immigration, Identity, Islam**. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc. 2017.

Musk, E., & Neuralink. Neuralink: A Neural Lace. **Neuralink Official Website**. 2019. Available at: www.neuralink.com

Musk, E.. "The Neuralink Presentation: A New Interface for the Brain." **The Journal of Neuroscience and Technology**. 2020.

Obstfeld M. and Taylor Alan M.- Global Capital Markets: Integration, Crisis, and Growth. Global capital markets : integration, crisis, and growth. Japan-U.S. Center Sanwa monographs on international financial markets. Includes bibliographical references and index. 2004. isbn 0-521-63317-6 **Cambridge University Press** 978-0-521-63317-8

OpenAI. **ChatGPT**. Accessed: 2023-02-08. 2023. url: <https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt/>

Orwell G. **Nineteen Eighty-Four**, London, Secker & Warburg, 1949, ISBN 0-451-52493-4.

Osborne, Martin J., and Carolyn Pitchik. "Equilibrium in Hotelling's Model of Spatial Competition." **Econometrica**, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 911–22. 1987. JSTOR, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1911035>. Accessed 19 Jan. 2024.

Roberts, Margaret E. Censored: Distraction and Diversion Inside China's Great Firewall. **Princeton University Press**, 2018. JSTOR, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvc77b21>. Accessed 19 Jan. 2024

Sahakian, B. J., & Morein-Zamir, S. "Professor, I've Forgotten My Meds: The Ethics of Cognitive Enhancement." **The Lancet**, 369(9571), 688-689. 2007

Sandberg, Anders (14 April 2014). "Ethics of brain emulations". **Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence**. 26 (3): 439–457. 2014. doi:10.1080/0952813X.2014.895113 (<https://doi.org/10.1080/0952813X.2014.895113>). S2CID 14545074 (<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:14545074>).

Schneider S. Artificial You: AI and the Future of Your Mind, **Princeton University Press**, 2019. ISBN 9780691180144

Searle, J. Twenty-one years in the Chinese room. In: J. Preston & M. Bishop (Eds.). Views into the Chinese room (pp. 51–69).2002. Oxford: **Oxford University Press**.

Stiglitz J. Globalization and its Discontents," **Journal of International Development**, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. New York : W. W. Norton., vol. 16(6), pages 897-905. 2002

Thaler, Richard H.. **The Winner's Curse: Paradoxes and Anomalies of Economic Life**. Princeton: Princeton University Press. 1992. ISBN 0-691-01934-7.

Tetlock, Philip E.; Gardner, Dan. **Superforecasting - The Art and Science of Prediction**. **New York: Crown**. 2015. ISBN 978-0-8041-3669-3

Vernon L. Smith REFLECTIONS ON HUMAN ACTION AFTER 50 YEARS **Cato Journal**, Vol. 19, No. 2, Fall. 1999 retrieved 20-01-2024 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20061105114721/http://www.cato.org/pubs/journal/cj19n2/cj19n2-1.pdf>

Volpe e, G. **Italian Elitism and the Reshaping of Democracy in the United States**. 2021. Abingdon, Oxon; New York: Routledge.

UNESCO. **Quick Start Guide are adapted from Harnessing the era of Artificial Intelligence in higher education: A Manual for Higher Education Stakeholders**, to be published by UNESCO IESALC in 2023. This publication is available in Open Access under the Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/igo/>). Accessed 20-01-2024 at https://www.iesalc.unesco.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/ChatGPT-and-Artificial-Intelligence-in-higher-education-Quick-Start-guide_EN_FINAL.pdf